

1. Guides

Guide Community

1- Sociological Profile

Name and Surname(s)/Age/Marital Status/Occupation and Education Level/Other Qualifications/Career Path/Social Origin/Geographic Trajectory and Settlement Process in the Locality

2- Establishment of settlement and socio-political organization of the locality

History of settlement (first settlers, political and religious authorities)

The first neighborhoods and their inhabitants (neighborhoods today)

Relationships between the different ethnic groups

Political/customary authorities

Number of localities around the protected forest

Settlement history of the different localities

Relationships between your locality and other localities

3- The legal and legitimate standards for the management of natural resources

Knowledge of local social norms regarding natural resources (land, forests, water)

Knowledge of social norms in other localities concerning natural resources (land, forests, water)

Knowledge of national texts and laws concerning natural resources (land, forests, water)

Implementation of these texts, the difficulties encountered in implementation, and the reasons for them

4- Traditional land management methods

Land management rules

Land authorities and management methods

Changes in management methods/Reasons for changes

Assessment of changes

5- Land commodification

The process of establishing commodification

Actors in commodification/Amount according to surface area

Consequences of commodification: social, religious, cultural, lineage-related, and familial

Assessments of the changes

Final remarks

Thank you for your time

Resource persons guide

1- Sociological Profile

Name and Surname(s)/Profession and level of study

2- The legal and legitimate standards for the management of natural resources

Knowledge of local social norms regarding natural resources (land, forests, water)

Knowledge of social norms in other localities concerning natural resources (land, forests, water)

Knowledge of national texts and laws concerning natural resources (land, forests, water)

Implementation of these texts, the difficulties encountered in implementation, and the reasons for them

3- Traditional land management methods

Land management rules

Land authorities and management methods

Changes in management methods/Reasons for changes

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4- Land commodification

The process of establishing commodification

Actors in commodification/Amount according to surface area

Consequences of commodification: social, religious, cultural, lineage-related, and familial

Assessments of the changes

Final remarks

Thank you for your time

2. Table showing the profile of respondents

N°	Type of interview	Interviewee profile	Gender	Number	Locality
01	Individual interview	Customary manager	Male	2	Nasso
				2	Dindéresso
02	Individual interview	Indigenous landowner	Male	3	Dindéresso
				2	Nasso
03	Individual interview	Indigenous landowner farmer	Male	2	Nasso
				2	Dindéresso
			Female	1	Nasso
				1	Dindéresso
04	Individual interview	Non-Indigenous	Male	1	Dindéresso
				1	Nasso
			Female	1	Nasso
				2	Dindéresso
05	Individual interview	Non-Indigenous landowner	Male	1	Nasso
				1	Dindéresso
			Female	1	Dindéresso
				1	Nasso
06	Individual interview	Administrative agent	Male	2	Bobo-Dioulasso
			Female	1	Nasso
07	Individual interview	Municipal authority	Male	2	Bobo-Dioulasso
08	Individual interview	Breeder	Male	1	Nasso
				2	Dindéresso
Total number of people surveyed				32	

3. Data analysis table according to variables

Variables		Verbatims
<i>Land availability</i>	<i>Profile, gender, age</i>	<p>What we heard from the elders is that the forest was established in 1933. According to them, it was the white people who sent the tree planters. They went to the Chief in Dioulassoba, and the Chief said that, in his opinion, the best land was in the Dindéresso and Nasso area. If they wanted to do this work, they should go there; that's where the trees could thrive. That's how the forest was established. So they informed Nasso and Dindéresso, who didn't agree at first, but as they say, force intervened. According to the elders, even along the riverbank, cornfields were destroyed. If a plant fell on a corn stalk, the corn was uprooted to make way for a tree. That's why we say that force didn't come at night, force came during the day; it simply means that force was used against them, otherwise they wouldn't have accepted it. And over time, the entire area was taken over and designated as a protected forest.</p> <p>Our parents lived where the Nasso seminary is today. It was Chief Soukon of Nasso who allowed them to settle there. But the Europeans came and took over the land to build the seminary in 1921. So, our parents moved to where the university is now, before the Dindéresso Classified Forest was established. They created the Dindéresso Classified Forest in 1936. When they were asked to leave that site, it was Chief Soukon of Nasso who gave them the current location. We were born here, but our older brothers were born at other sites.</p> <p>From what we had learned, our parents were initially settled in Nasso, where the current Seminary is located. When that area was given to the Catholics to build the seminary, they moved to the present site of Nazi Boni University. Later, with the creation of the Dindéresso Classified Forest, the authorities at the time, who were settlers, said it would be impossible for herders to live so close to it. Therefore, the authorities asked the village chief of Nasso to find them another area. That's how</p>
	Village authority in Dindéresso; Male; 65 years old; Illiterate	
	Livestock farmer in Nasso; Male; 54 years old; Illiterate	
	Livestock farmer in Nasso; Male; 54 years old; Illiterate	

		they came to this area and settled there with the permission of the village chief of Nasso.
	Livestock farmer in Nasso; Male; 54 years old; Illiterate	Before, he had the bush and we earned a lot of milk from the cows. We didn't have to go far to graze our cattle because there was plenty of grass around our concessions.
	Community authority in Dindéresso; Male; 48 years old; Illiterate	What we heard from the elders is that it was the white people who sent the tree plantation [exotic trees]. They went to the chief in Dioulassoba, and the chief said that, in his opinion, the best land was in the Dindéresso and Nasso area. If they wanted to create a forest, they should go there; that's where the trees would thrive. That's how the forest was created. So they informed Nasso and Dindéresso. They [those villages] hadn't agreed, but as they say, force came in broad daylight. According to what the elders said, even along the riverbank, cornfields were ravaged. If a plant fell on an ear of corn, the corn was pulled up to plant the tree seedling. That's why we say that force didn't come at night; force came during the day. It simply means that they were forced; otherwise, they wouldn't have agreed. And over time, the entire area was taken over to become a protected forest.
	Community authority in Nasso; Male; 53 years old; Illiterate	Bana means bamboo; in Bobo, we call it Ban. The village's founder was a hunter. During his travels, he discovered a large population of wild animals and a dense bamboo grove, so the village was named after the bamboo. When asked where it was, he said it was where there was a lot of bamboo. Those who came to see the place then adopted the name "Ban" for the village, which means "Ban" in Bobo. That's what Bana means.

<i>Land scarcity</i>	Farmer in Nasso; Male; 54 years old; Illiterate	I grew up in Bana. I went to Ivory Coast for an adventure, for 10 years, from 1982 to 1992. I returned to Bobo in 1992 to take over my father's cattle herd. At that time, we were in Sector 21, next to the Hayatt pharmacy, which was an undeveloped area, and the National High School was just the bush. When they developed the area, they demolished our house sometime between 1998 and 2000. After that, we rented before buying our own plot of land when the Belle Ville neighborhood was developed in 2001.
	Dindéresso Indigenous; Female; 41 years old; Primary education	When I used to come here, life was good [due to marital lineage]. There was market gardening; we grew tomatoes, cabbages, the crops were varied here. But nowadays, life here has become hard. Before, in this village, whether you grew vegetables or not, when it was daytime, if you went to the riverbank where they grew vegetables, if someone was harvesting cabbages, they might give you some in a small basin. If you went further, you would get the same amount again, and you wouldn't even be able to carry it back to the village. Today, we are suffering; life has become hard here.
	Nasso, a livestock breeder; Male; 45 years old; Illiterate	Before, he had the bush and we earned a lot of milk from our cows. We didn't have to go far to graze our cattle because there was plenty of grass around our properties.

	Community authority in Nasso; Male; 53 years old; Illiterate	Things have deteriorated because of the traditional leaders. There are those responsible for the bush, the rain, and the Do (a local term for a specific type of watercourse). If these ceremonies no longer follow their proper course, things will go wrong. If the village chief no longer does things the way they used to, things will fall apart. The same goes for the bush leader; if things aren't done correctly, the bush will be ruined. Before, every year, the elders made sacrifices at the Kou River. They would prepare Dolo (a local beer), along with a sheep and some chickens, to perform these rituals. But nowadays, these sacrifices are no longer made, and that's what has caused the water level in the river to decrease.
<i>Lineage property</i>	Landowner and farmer in Dindéresso; Male; 37 years old; Illiterate	When land is sold in a community, it's inevitable that there will be conflicts; that's the reason for our problems. These conflicts have led to fights among us Indigenous people. Often, within the same extended family, some want to sell the land and others don't, because it wasn't the traditional practice. The problem arises because you were born into a situation where your parents didn't sell the land. If they did sell the land, you wouldn't be able to find any land to live on.
	Community authority in Dindéresso; Male; 62 years old; Illiterate	Dindéresso performs rituals with Bana. We perform these rituals together because Soungalodaga, Bana, Toukôrô, and Dinderesso are like one family. They are brothers who founded these villages. So we hold traditional ceremonies together. The people of Bana even attended my mother's funeral, which took place a few days ago [She passed away on Sunday, June 2, 2018, and the funeral was held on Wednesday, June 6, 2018]. People came from Bana to participate in the burial.
	Livestock farmer in Nasso; Male; 45 years old; Illiterate	Often, they use cattle tracks to make fields; these are the problems we face, especially with those from Wolokoto. When we were children, there were a few Bobo families living near us. But at that time, there were no problems between us. He farmed and respected the boundaries of our land, so there were no issues. This old Bobo man had a very good relationship with our grandfather; it was like family. The elders of the past were loyal; they kept their promises. But since this old Bobo

		man passed away, his grandson came and took his land, and that's when the problems started.
<i>Family property</i>	Native to Nasso; Male; 38 years old; Illiterate	Often, they use cattle tracks to make fields; these are the problems we face, especially with those from Wolokoto. When we were children, there were a few Bobo families living near us. But at that time, there were no problems between us. He farmed and respected the boundaries of our land, so there were no issues. This old Bobo man had a very good relationship with our grandfather; it was like family. The elders of the past were loyal; they kept their promises. But since this old Bobo man passed away, his grandson came and took his land, and that's when the problems started.
	Administrative officer in Bobo-Dioulasso; Male; 42 years old; Junior High School Diploma Level	[Iyeu!] Meanwhile, if you sold a field within the family, it was a problem. In our time, we didn't dare sell a field. We might give the field to someone so that person could find something to eat. Isn't it appearances that led to the sale of fields? If I tell myself that you have a motorcycle, then I must have a motorcycle too, even though I haven't done the work of owning a motorcycle. That's what leads to selling fields. Otherwise, it wouldn't have been done. [Iyeu!] You wouldn't dare, and you wouldn't even do it. At that time, all the elders were united, and when you did it, the village chief would call you, and you would tell the elders the reasons that led you to do it. Some people even fled the village to go elsewhere.
	Native to Nasso; Female; 41 years old; Illiterate	Before, he had communal fields for the whole family. But as families grew, the land problem arose. If you have 10 hectares for the whole family, and each son starts his own household, eventually, 10 hectares won't be enough. If you decide to divide it, each family won't even have half a hectare, and even that won't be sufficient.

<i>Individual property</i>	Traditional authority, Nasso; Male; 63 years old; Illiterate	Nowadays, you could say that some people don't have any fields; if a father of a family doesn't have more than one hectare, you could say that you don't have a field.
	Native to Dindéresso; Female; 50 years old; Illiterate	They've caused us problems with the family. He has two hectares, I have three hectares, and the other one's land is also less than three hectares. And there are many people in the family. They're going to give you two plots each, you're going to put them together before gathering the whole family to divide them. What good will that do you, because you can't build there?
	Community authority in Nasso; Male; 63 years old; Illiterate	The bush is thinning out, and we now live in close proximity; we no longer have fields to cultivate. This is the fault of the local officials; they are the ones who came to develop the housing estates. The estates have caused us too many problems in the village; we no longer have fields to cultivate, and it has contributed to breaking up families, because if you have a large family and you are given two hectares, what good can that do for the whole family except cause fights?
	Indigenous landowner in Dinderesso; Male; 58 years old; Illiterate	When land is sold in a community, it's inevitable that there will be conflicts; that's the root of our problems. These conflicts have even led to fights among us, the local people. Often, within the same family, some may want to sell the land while others don't, because it wasn't the traditional practice. The problem arises because you were born into a situation where your parents didn't sell the land, because if they did, you wouldn't be able to acquire any land.
<i>Land commodification</i>	Foreigner in Nasso; Male; 31 years old; Illiterate	Before, people didn't sell land, but nowadays money and the desire for money are leading young people to sell it. Some sell to buy a motorcycle or a car. I want a motorcycle, I also want a car, but I will never sell the land because I was born on this land and my parents didn't sell it, so I'm not going to sell it.

	Community leader in Dindéresso; Male; 48 years old; Primary education	Before, people didn't sell land, but nowadays, money and the desire for money lead people to sell their land. Some sell to buy a motorcycle or a car. I want a motorcycle, I also want a car, but I will never sell the land because I was born on this land and my parents didn't sell it, so I'm not going to sell it.
	Non-native farmer in Nasso; Male; 39 years old; Primary education	These days, people have become self-reliant, and land sales have increased significantly. Selling land has become a trend. The reason for selling land is the lure of money. It's hard for some to resist when they hear about money. Now the selling price has gone up; before, a hectare would sell for ridiculously low prices, between 90, 69 and 181,38 USD in the 2000s. But nowadays, if you don't have 544,14 or even 906,9 USD, you can't buy a hectare because there's no land left. If you don't have the means and you're in a difficult situation, if a rich person makes you an offer, you'll sell your land. That's the real problem in our village right now. Even tomorrow, people will do it, even though they know they shouldn't sell land.
	Dinderesso Community Authority; Male; 62 years old; Illiterate	When land is sold in a community, it's inevitable that there will be conflicts; that's the root of our problems. These conflicts have even led to fights among us, the local people. Often, within the same family, some may want to sell the land while others don't, because it wasn't the traditional practice. The problem arises because you were born into a situation where your parents didn't sell the land, because if they did, you wouldn't be able to acquire any land.

	<p>Dindéresso Indigenous; Male; 37 years old; Primary Education</p>	<p>Nowadays, the population has grown significantly, and land sales have increased dramatically, whereas before this wasn't the case. Selling land has become a trend. When you sell land to someone, they cut it down and do whatever they want with it. The reason for selling land is the lure of money. It's difficult for some to resist when they hear about money. Now the selling price has increased; before, a hectare would sell for 90, 69 and 181,38 USD in the 2000s. But nowadays, if you don't have 544,14 or even 906,9 USD, you can't buy a hectare because there's no land available. If you don't have the means and you're in a difficult situation, if a rich person makes you an offer, you'll sell your land. That's the real problem here right now. Even tomorrow people will do it, and they know that we mustn't sell the land.</p>
	<p>Indigenous landowner Nasso; Male; 28 years old; Primary education</p>	<p>If we were to follow the current trend, there would come a time when we wouldn't have a single tree like that anymore, except for those that have been planted. There's also the problem of land sales; you, who take your land to sell, what will your children, when they are born, find? And let's not even talk about your grandchildren.</p>
	<p>Dindéresso Indigenous; Female; 31 years old; Primary Education</p> <p>1 551.31 X 6 000</p>	<p>The preparation of dolo (local beer) here is organized by day; my selling day is Wednesday. If you pay 10,88 USD for a tin of millet, you can get 18,13 USD after expenses (I don't pay for the bundle of firewood). I participated in the logging operation in the forest organized by the GGF (Groupement Forestier de France) this year; I worked three days. The men and I cut down the trees together to stack them in cords. After the total amount was divided, I received 15,78 USD for my three days of work.</p>

	Town Hall employee; Male; 53 years old; Junior High School Diploma	If the authorities prevented people from selling land, land sales would decrease. Imagine you go to Bobo to get the paperwork for selling land and they tell you they no longer issue such documents; you won't be able to sell any more land. You found a piece of land and you sell it; if it were selling, you wouldn't have found it. Therefore, it's the authorities' responsibility to ensure that land is no longer sold. Land sales should only concern urban plots; rural and peri-urban lands are reserved for agricultural use, and if they are sold, the farmers will have nothing left to do.
<i>Conflict</i>	Indigenous landowner in Dindéresso; Male; 58 years old; High school diploma	We have many problems today, and these problems are land-related. Now, these family members are fighting. You'll find people from the same family fighting over land. Some family members want to sell the land, and others don't. So, they're forced to sell because no one listens to the head of the family. Everyone thinks they're free. This is the source of our problems today.
	Dindéresso Indigenous; Female; 39 years old; Illiterate	These problems are with those in another neighborhood; they're closer to us. This village is called Sangama. These issues arose because of land disputes. We had land between our village and theirs that belongs to us. Some of our villagers were farming there, and they're demanding that those who farmed there leave. However, in our grandparents' time, they didn't mark a boundary between them regarding land. And now that the elders have passed away, they claim that land belongs to them. We will maintain the boundaries our grandparents left us; we cannot accept what they want, and they also say they cannot accept what we want. For us, it's impossible because our grandparents farmed this land, so we cannot give it up to them. That's how our conflict began.

	<p>Foreigner in Nasso; Male; 43 years old; High school diploma</p>	<p>A land dispute arose between us and the people of Wolonkoto. We went to the Village Development Committee (CVD) in Nasso, but received no solution. We then took the matter to the gendarmerie in Bobo-Dioulasso, again without success. Finally, we went to see the chiefs of Nasso and Wolonkoto to try and resolve the issue.</p>
	<p>Livestock farmer in Bobo-Dioulasso; Male; 51 years old; Illiterate</p>	<p>These are problems; the land has shrunk, and there's no longer a passage for cattle. Nothing has made the situation difficult except the sale of the land. Even though they want to sell the land and we want to buy it, they won't sell to us. They prefer to sell to other people.</p>